

THE CONCEPTS OF TERMINOLOGY, TERM FIELD AND TERM SYSTEM

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Due to their consistency, the terms of a particular field of science, technologies or fields of activity are closely interconnected with each other and united in a structured organization. Until recently time structured organization of the terms of a particular industry knowledge was called "terminology". In recent decades, domestic linguists the word "terminal system" is also used, and much more actively than "terminology".

Linguists do not have a common opinion on the distinction between concepts terminology and terminology. One of the reasons for this is that that there is still no clear definition of the terminological system. Mechanistic systems are systems whose quality is equal to the sum properties of its elements, taken in isolation from each other. At mechanistic systems, elements can exist autonomously.

The term system corresponds to the system of concepts of a certain sphere of knowledge and is a set of terms determined by the culture of the country and the mentality of the people.

In this regard, there has recently been talk not only of professional picture of the world, but also about the national scientific picture of the world. The national scientific picture of the world is the national picture of the world, "imprinted in the terminological systems (language of science) of one or another national language".

On the problem of differentiating the terms "terminology" and terminological system" V.M. Leichik [2, 156] approaches from different positions. One of grounds for distinguishing between terminology and terminological system, he considers scientific theory or concept. According to V.M. Leychik [2], the terminology is a collection of terms not united by any theory or concept, respectively, not reflecting all the concepts of this science or branches of technology; terminological system, on the contrary, is a set of terms, formed on the basis of one theory or concept and reflecting connections all concepts of a certain field of knowledge.

As the next distinguishing feature of the terminological system a number of linguists consider her orderliness. According to scientists, terminology appears spontaneously, and the terminological system is created artificially and is formed as a result of ordering terminology into an organized system of terms with recorded in industry dictionaries and classification models relations between them.

However, modern terminology is also created artificially. "The terminology of the science of the new time is an artificially formed lexical layer, each the unit of which has certain restrictions for its use and optimal conditions for its existence and development".

Not all researchers share the opinion that the terminological system systemic, and the terminology is not systemic. However, proponents of this approach terminology is understood not as a simple collection of words, but as a system interrelated terms-words and terminological phrases, the systemic connection of which is manifested in synonymous, antonymic, generic and whole-private relations within the same terminology. Thus, V.A. Tatarinov [5] believes that any modern the terminology is systemic and subject to ordering, i.e. process unification of terminological units for the purpose of their successful use in professional and scientific communication.

Terminology as a system was also represented by one of the first domestic terminologists, the founder of the terminological school in our country D.S. Lotte: "should not be a simple collection words, but a system of words and phrases, in a certain way among themselves connected". [3, 109] Later, D.S. Lotte wrote that terminology is "not just a list of terms, but a semiological expression of a certain system concepts, which, in turn, reflects a certain scientific worldview". [3, 103]

A significant part of industry terms in the terminology and terminological system affect the lexico-semantic processes of polysemy, synonymy and antonyms. Both terminology and terminological system reflect the system concepts of a certain field of science, technology or field of activity, and also national self-consciousness, which explains some of the differences in naming equivalent terms in different languages. Scientists often identify the term field and the term system, and in this regard, in modern terminological studies instead of the term "term field" is used "term system".

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